

Manufacturing and Improvement of Springbacked Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastic Sandwich Structures

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Introduction

Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastics (CFRTP)

Properties

Suitability for lightweight application

- CFRTP can be reshaped when reaching a specific temperature.
- This material has excellent performance in high-speed molding and is suitable for recycling.

Figure 1: The application of example of CFRTP [1]

Springback phenomenon

Figure 2: Molding process of CFRTP products

Springback ratio: the thickness changed during the heating process.

Plenty contact points of fibers
 Residual stress during molding
 Stress release (Re-heated)
 Out of plane expansion

Figure 3: Springback process [2]

Sandwich structures

Figure 4: Various kinds of sandwich structures

Materials and Experiments

Materials

Skin: CF/PA6 UD sheet (Unidirectional carbon fiber sheet)
 Thickness: 132 μm

Core: CWT (Carbon fiber card web reinforced)
 V_f : 20%

Carbon fiber card web reinforced thermoplastic:

This material is manufactured by a novel carding process. Due to the manufacturing process of CWT sheets, the fiber orientation distribution is influenced by the moving direction of carding machine. Here, we defined the moving direction of the machine as the L direction of the material and the perpendicular direction as the T direction.

Figure 5: Manufacturing process of CWT material [6]

Manufacturing process of CWT-UD sandwich structures

My former research has proved that springback ratio 2-2.5 is the optimal springback ratio for CWT-UD sandwich structures. However, interlaminar properties is a serious problem in former research. During this research, one-step molding is used instead of two-step molding to save molding time and energy. At the same time, molding parameters were changed to improve interlaminar properties.

Figure 6: Manufacturing process of CWT-UD sandwich structures

Three-point bending test

Three-point bending tests are conducted by a universal testing machine. Specimen were set on the middle of span and then the three-point bending experiment started from the demarcation point of load (zero point which will read the load if one more displacement is made). Testing speed is 1 mm/min here.

Table 1: Specimen dimensions for three-point bending test.

	Dimension of specimen				Span length [mm]
	Length [mm]	Width [mm]	Thickness [mm]	SB ratio	
Two-280	84	35	3.4	2.4	56
One-275	84	35	3.3	2.3	56
One-265	84	35	3.3	2.3	56
One-265-C2	84	35	3.4	2.3	56
One-265-E1C2	100	35	4.1	1.7	64
Two-265-E1C2	100	35	4.1	1.7	64

Results and discussion

The observation of failure mode

Different failure models can be found due to various interfacial bonding properties. By investigating in the microstructure of fracture surface, the better binder between resin and carbon fibers can be found by improvement.

The results of static mechanical properties

Figure 7 Static mechanical properties of CWT-UD sandwich structures

The density of springback ratio 2.5 CWT-UD sandwich structures is about 0.9 g/cm³ and the floating structures such as lifeboats can be taken into account. More and more applications can be considered after waterproofing method is done in the future.

$$\rho \approx 0.9 \text{ g/cm}^3$$

Conclusions

In this study, we focused on the manufacturing and improvement of CWT-UD sandwich structures on the mechanical properties. The conclusion of this study is summarized below:

- The molding temperature and material set influence the interlaminar bonding properties.
- With proper manufacturing method, the delamination can be eliminated without sacrificing flexural strength. However, flexural stiffness is depressed due to the reduce of actual volume fraction of carbon fibers. This orientation needs to be promoted in the future.
- The substantial improvement of energy absorption will open a new road for application of automobiles such as bumpers. Moreover, the lower density can contribute to the practicality of this structure such as floating production system and so on in off-shore oilfield.

References

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